

EVALUATING THE MICRON LEVEL PHASE DISTRIBUTION IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES AND ITS EFFECT ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR USING 2D MODULUS MAPPING

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BACKGROUND

- Polymers matrix composites (PMCs) are rapidly emerging material systems for potential use in various sectors due to their low density and corrosion resistance.
- Among all polymers epoxies are the most preferred matrix materials due to low density, better stiffness, good adhesion to most reinforcements, high thermal stability, low shrinkage, low moisture absorption and ease of processing
- However, the biggest setback is its low fracture toughness. The best solution to overcome this is to reinforce epoxy with second phase, having high mechanical properties as well as light weight
- Conventional solution to this is the use of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP). However, the toughness and strength, imparted in such composites, are highly anisotropic in nature.
- Nanodiamond(ND) (a geometrical feature offering an entanglement-free nanoparticle) with maximum interfacial area compared to platelet and rodlike nanoparticles.
- Rich surface chemistry along with high mechanical properties makes it a desirable candidate as a reinforcement in epoxy matrix

OBJECTIVES

- To assess the potential of nanodiamond as a reinforcement to epoxy matrix
- Evaluating the effect of nanodiamond on mechanical and thermal behaviour of the composite structure and optimizing the composition
- Detailed microstructural analysis to understand the interfacial interaction between nanodiamond and epoxy. As well as understanding the main strengthening and toughening mechanism that governs mechanical behaviour

MATERIALS

Matrix Material
Epoxy – Epofine 5052
Curing agent- (hardener) Finehard 5052
Mixing ratio 100:38;
Density-1.10 – 1.20 g/cm³

Reinforcement
Nanodiamonds (NDs)
Particle Size <10 nm
Surface area 200-450 m²/g
Density 3.5 g/cm³

METHODOLOGY

CHARACTERIZATION

Mechanical

- Uniaxial Tensile Test
- Fracture Toughness(3 point bend test)
- Nanoindentation
- Tensile test was done using ASTM D638- V. 3 point bend test was done to calculate fracture toughness(K_{IC}) using ASTM D5045-99.
- Nanoindentation was done in Hysitron TI-950 Triboindenter with atleast 20 indents per sample were taken to evaluate hardness and elastic modulus

Thermomechanical

- Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)
- Storage Modulus
- Tanδ
- Glass transition temperature (T_g)
- NanoDMA
- Storage modulus

Microstructural

- To verify
- Dispersability
- Presence of defects (porosity, cracks)
- Interfacial interaction
- Failure mode
- Toughening mechanism, FE-SEM(Carl-Zeiss Ultra Plus) was used in this study

RESULTS

Fig. 1. (a) Stress-Strain curve, (b) UTS and (c) % strain for various composition of ND/Epoxy composite

Fig. 2. Fracture toughness for various ND/Epoxy composition

Fig. 3 FE-SEM images for fractured surface of (a, b & c) for epoxy, (d, e & f) for 0.1 wt% ND, (g, h & i) for 0.3 wt% ND and (j, k & l) for 1 wt% ND at different magnification

- Strengthening is due to the presence of uniformly distributed stronger reinforcement, which shares the load transferred to the matrix through strong interface
- Toughening is due to the series of deflection and pinning of crack front, when it encounters a strong impenetrable reinforcement

From fig. 3 (a, d, g & j) it can be clearly seen that with the addition of ND, the fracture morphology changes from brittle to somewhat ductile. As ND content increases from 0.1 wt% to 1 wt% (fig. 3 d, g & j), the crack path becomes more branched and tortuous (fig. 3 e, h & k). This is because the crack front encounters more number of impenetrable obstacles and gets deflected again and again until it loses all its energy

Good dispersion and strong interfacial interaction between ND and epoxy can be clearly evidenced from Fig. 3 (f & i). As no free lying nanodiamond can be seen on the surface even at very high magnification. In fact, fracture surface gives an impression of being coated with polymer layer

At 1 wt%, agglomeration of ND and the porosity generated due to it can be clearly seen. Fig. 3(l) clearly shows the crack gets deflected by the impenetrable agglomerate of ND, thus increasing the fracture toughness, but not as high as in case of uniformly distributed ND

Fig. 5. Typical DMA results (a) tanδ curve and (b) Storage modulus for various composition of ND/Epoxy composite as a function of temperature

ND(wt%)	epoxy	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.5	1
E _g (GPa)(30°C)	0.76	0.82	0.97	0.98	1.11	1.41
E _g (GPa)(150°C)	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Tanδ	1.1	0.87	0.86	0.86	0.79	0.75
T _g (°C)	75	84	84.9	85.3	85	85

- Storage modulus signifies stiffness. Up to 0.1wt% no significant improvement is seen due to the low amount of filler available to interact with the matrix.
- Increasing the amount of ND further resulted in a significant increase of modulus. The maximum improvement is - 85 % with 1 wt% ND.
- The retention of higher modulus by composites above room temperature, as compared to neat epoxy, is due to the restricted segmental mobility of polymer structure
- Reinforcing epoxy with ND increased glass transition temperature by ~ 10° C

CONCLUSIONS

- The strength, ductility and fracture toughness of nanocomposites was found to increase with ND content up to 0.3 wt%, above which agglomeration starts reducing its properties. However for all compositions, the properties were better than neat epoxy.
- Addition of 1wt% ND has resulted a significant improvement in hardness and stiffness by 470% and 100%, respectively, over neat epoxy.
- DMA studies showed improvement in storage modulus. The improvement achieved was almost equal to that observed through nanoindentation studies, with increase in glass transition temperature, by ~ 10°C.
- 2D modulus mapping clearly showed the mechanical behaviour of epoxy matrix is influenced with the addition of nanodiamond. It also showed how the quality of dispersion and interaction between reinforcement and matrix dictates mechanical properties with and without loading.

Fig. 4. (a) Load vs displacement plot and (b) Variation of Elastic modulus and Hardness for different composition

- Modulus of Elasticity (E) and hardness improved by 94% and 470 % with 1wt% ND, which is the highest improvement achieved.
- Uniformly distributed ND provides high resistance to the matrix against deformation, thus improving its hardness. Strong interfacial interaction of ND-epoxy increases stiffness.

MODULUS MAPPING AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Fig. 6. (a) Schematic of tensile sample used for modulus mapping and (b) Storage modulus maps for epoxy and ND-epoxy before tensile stress is applied

Fig. 7. Storage modulus maps for (a) epoxy before tensile and epoxy ND composite (b) before tensile and (c) after tensile test

Fig. 8. Storage modulus maps for (a) epoxy and (b) epoxy-ND composite at ~ 1-2 mm from fractured surface tip

Fig. 9. (a) Schematic representation of the homogenization approach for the periodic microstructure, (b) meshed RVE containing randomly distributed circular particles in the continuous matrix, (c) RVE subjected to the uniaxial tensile strain, (d and e) reaction force and strain energy curve obtained under the specific loading and boundary conditions, (f) convergence study for modulus evaluation against number of elements, (g) comparative variation of effective elastic modulus with weight fraction of ND obtained from the numerical and experimental analysis, (h) the von-Mises stress distribution for the RVE and (i) Storage modulus map for ND-epoxy

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